

Complex Treatment of Deep Burns Based on Surgical Necrectomy and Modern Biotechnological Methods

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Abstract

The comparative analysis of the results of complex treatment in 86 patients with deep burns (total body surface area 850%) using combined autodermoplasty (CADP) with cultured fibroblasts in gel or on carriers, versus traditional autodermoplasty (ADP), demonstrated that early surgical necrectomy combined with fibroblast transplantation significantly improves wound healing due to rapid epithelization and graft survival.

Keywords

Keywords: Deep burns, Combined autodermoplasty, Cultured fibroblasts, Skin regeneration, Surgical necrectomy

Main Body

This preprint is based on the Russian-language article titled " ". The full English translation is in progress and will reflect the detailed study results, methodology, and clinical findings presented in the original publication.